

SPECIFIC MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS/CARBON EPOXY COMPOSITES FOR MARINE APPLICATIONS

A. Valenza, V. Fiore, G. Di Bella
University of Palermo
Viale delle Scienze, 90128 Palermo
valenza@unipa.it; fiore@dicpm.unipa.it; gdibella@ingegneria.unime.it

SUMMARY

The aim of this work is to study the influence of an uniaxial carbon fabric layer on the mechanical performances of a glass mat/epoxy composite used for marine applications. All structures are realized, at room temperature, with vacuum bagging technique. Flexural tests are carried out in order to evaluate the specific properties of the composite.

Keywords: hybrid, fibre orientation, specific property, flexural test

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the specific strength of the glass composites is higher than that of the metals used for marine applications (i.e. steel or aluminium alloy), whereas their specific stiffness is lower. In the marine ships the strength is a critical parameter for the hull structures, the stiffness is critical for the topside structures due to it influences the ship stability. Then it is needed that the composite materials have better specific stiffness than the metals [1].

In this research work, to increase the mechanical specific performance of the glass composites, a layer of glass mat has been replaced with one of uniaxial carbon fabric. Following this way, a set of hybrid laminates by varying the position and the orientation of the uniaxial carbon fabric has been produced and tested.

Hybrid composites are usually used when a combination of properties of different types of fibres wants to be achieved, i.e. carbon-kevlar reinforced epoxy which combines strength and impact resistance [2] or glass-carbon reinforced epoxy which gives a strong materials at a reasonable price with also higher fatigue performance and environmental resistance compared to glass composites [3].

Materials and manufacturing

All composite structures are realized at room temperature with a single lamination using the vacuum bagging, a technique that involves an initial hand lay-up phase and then the polymerization of the matrix in a flexible bag in which negative pressure is reached by a

vacuum pump. All laminates were cured at room temperature for 24 h and post-cured at 60° C for 8 h.

The stacking sequence of the reference laminate (called “Mat”) consists of six layers of E-glass mat (randomly oriented fibres, with density of 450 g/m²) in a matrix of epoxy resin (Sicommin SR 8500).

To evaluate the influence of carbon, each layer of glass mat has been replaced with one layer of uniaxial carbon fabric. Moreover for each position of the carbon layer, two structures have been realized; i.e. using respectively a different carbon fibre orientation: parallel (0°) and perpendicular (90°) to the x direction showed in figure 1.

Figure 1. Laminate geometric configuration.

The uniaxial carbon fabric is supplied by Bentontex (FTS GV 320). This is an fabric produced using UHM carbon fiber stitched with a 20 g/m² fiberglass knitting thread. The areal weight of the fabric is 320 g/m². The carbon fiber had a tensile strength of 2.5 GPa and a tensile modulus of 640 GPa .

Figure 2 illustrates the architectures of carbon fabric and mat glass.

Figure 2. (a) Carbon fabric and (b) E- glass mat

Twelve hybrid structures have been produced; In table 1 both the position and the orientation of uniaxial carbon fabric in the hybrid laminates are reported.

Table 1. Position and orientation of uniaxial carbon in the hybrid laminates produced.

Sample	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
position	layer 1	layer 2	layer 3	layer 4	layer 5	layer 6
orientation	0° - 90°	0° - 90°	0° - 90°	0° - 90°	0° - 90°	0° - 90°

In figure 3 (a-c) the upper sides of C1 samples (or the lower sides of C6 samples) with carbon fibre perpendicular and parallel to the x direction, respectively, are shown.

In figure 3 (b-d) a side of a reference sample (“all glass”) and the section of C1 sample are shown respectively.

Figure 3. Hybrid laminates.

Mechanical characterization

Three point bending tests are carried out according to ASTM D 790, by using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) mod. 3365 by Instron, equipped with a load cell of 5 KN.

Flexural tests are performed on each of the thirteen structures realized (twelve hybrid and the glass reference), using five prismatic samples with dimensions 2.5 x 20 x 96 mm. For all tests, the span length is equal to 80 mm and cross-head speed to 4.26 mm/min

Measurement of density

Three specimens with dimensions 2.5 x 2.5 mm are cut from each structure realized and their densities determined using the water displacement method by measuring their weights in air and in water.

In table 2 the average values of the laminate densities are reported:

Table 2. Average densities of the laminates

Sample	Mat		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
density [g/cm ³]	1.394	0°	1.387	1.328	1.323	1.347	1.335	1.320
		90°	1.342	1.339	1.327	1.309	1.323	1.308

Mechanical results

In table 3 the mechanical properties of the reference laminates are reported.

Table 3. Mechanical properties of the reference laminate “Mat”

E [GPa]	σ [MPa]	E/ ρ [GPa/g/cm ³]	σ/ρ [MPa/g/cm ³]
8.97 ± 0.7	204.64 ± 9.88	6.43 ± 0.5	146.8 ± 7.08

In figures 4 - 5 the specific properties of the laminates are shown:

- for the perpendicular orientation of the uniaxial carbon, the specific properties do not show an improvement compared to those of the “Mat” laminate;
- for the parallel orientation the increase is evident.

Figure 4. Specific modulus of the laminates.

Particularly, as regard the specific modulus it is possible to observe that:

- ✓ For the perpendicular (90°) orientation of the carbon layer, the specific flexural modulus varies between 6.22 ± 0.37 GPa/(g/cm³) and 8.01 ± 1.18 GPa/(g/cm³) for the “C6” and “C2” structures, respectively.
- ✓ For the parallel orientation (0°) of the uniaxial carbon to the x direction, we have obtained great increases of the specific stiffness particularly by replacing the external layers of glass mat. To be precise, the specific flexural modulus of the “C1” and “C6” structures result higher of about 222 % and 258 % compared to this one of the reference laminate, respectively. For the “C2” and “C5” structures we have obtained lower improvements (59 % and 64 %, respectively).

By replacing the internal layers of mat glass with uniaxial carbon, the specific stiffness of the hybrid structures do not increase compared to this one of the reference laminates. To be precise, the “C3” and “C4” structures show small improvements of the specific modulus, equal to 25 % and 15 %, respectively.

Figure 5. Specific strength of the laminates.

As regard to specific flexural strength it is possible to notice that:

- ✓ In the cases of carbon layer orientation at 90° to the x direction, the hybrid composites do not show high variations of this specific mechanical property compared to this one of the reference laminate.

For the perpendicular (90°) orientation of the carbon layer, the specific flexural strength varies between 122.5 ± 10.3 MPa/(g/cm³) and 156 ± 4.7 MPa/(g/cm³) for the “C6” and “C5” structures.

- ✓ By orienting the carbon layer parallel to the x direction, we have obtained higher improvements than the previous cases. Particularly for the “C6” structure, the increase of the specific strength reaches the 127 % compared to this one of the reference laminate. The other structures show increases of this specific property around to 30% except for the “C3” (13.6%) and “C4” (-1.4 %) structures.

It is important to evidence that, for the cross angle of the carbon layer equal to 0°, the average values of specific modulus of the “C1” and “C6” structures (20.7 and 23.0 GPa/g/cm³, respectively) are comparable to this one of a aluminium alloy (~22 GPa/g/cm³) or a steel (~24 GPa/g/cm³, data from [1]) commonly used in marine application.

Furthermore these hybrid structures keep specific strength (192 and 334 MPa/g/cm³, respectively) higher than those of aluminium alloy (~118 MPa/g/cm³) or steel (~64 MPa/g/cm³, data from [1]).

Preliminary flexural tests were performed on aluminium alloy (AA6016-T4) in order to know the values of specific modulus and strength of this reference material.

This result shows that, by replacing an external layer of glass mat with one of uniaxial carbon fabric parallel to the x direction, we obtain a hybrid composites that are well

suiting for constructing both hulls and the topside structures of a ship replacing the reference metals.

Conclusions

In the marine ships the strength is a critical parameter for the hull structures while the stiffness is critical for the topside structures due to it influences the ship stability. Since the specific stiffness of glass composites is lower than those of the metal (i.e steel or aluminium alloys) commonly used in the marine field, these composites are not well suited for constructing the topside structures of a ship.

The objective of this work is to increase the specific stiffness of GFRP composite replacing one layer of glass mat with one of uniaxial carbon fabric in order to use these hybrid materials even for the topside structures of a ship.

The influence of carbon on the tensile specific mechanical properties was analysed by realising and testing twelve hybrid structures: each layer of glass mat of the reference laminate has been replaced with one layer of uniaxial carbon fabric oriented at 0° and 90° to the x direction.

The mechanical results show that by replacing one external layer of glass mat with one of uniaxial carbon fabric parallel to the x direction, we obtain structures with comparable values of specific modulus and strength than those of the metals commonly used in marine field and, for this reason, these hybrid laminates can be used even for the topside structures of a ship.

References

1. Shivakumar K.N., Swaminathan G., Sharpe M.; "Carbon/vinyl ester composites for enhanced performance in marine applications", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 2006; 25: 1101-1116.
2. Dorey G., Sidey G.R., Hutchings J.; "Impact properties of carbon fibre/Kevlar 49 fibre hybrid composites", *Composites* 1978; 9: 25-32.
3. Shan Y., Liao K.; "Environmental fatigue behaviour and life prediction of unidirectional glass-carbon epoxy hybrid composites", *International Journal of Fatigue* 2002; 24: 847-859.